

Report on technologies and Practices

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1. Summary

An extensive review of soil management practices in agricultural, urban and forestry land at European field sites has been carried out. The study also compiled findings on land manager acceptance and adoption likelihood for soil health-improving technologies and practices. Results indicated that land managers implemented practices that minimized soil disturbance, utilized organic amendments, and incorporated new woody biomass and living roots to enhance soil health. Across all land-use types, the introduction of new woody biomass proved effective in reducing surface pollution, increasing soil carbon content, and promoting biodiversity. However, these benefits were not sustained once the trees matured.

In forestry areas, management strategies which reduce harvesting-associated compaction were largely effective, but dependent upon site conditions including soil type, texture, slope and underlying bulk density. The study revealed significant variations in the efficacy of soil health improvement strategies between cool temperate and Mediterranean climate zones. Furthermore, evidence indicated that economic and social constraints influenced land manager acceptance of these technologies and practices. By integrating findings on soil health benefits and adoption, the authors identified areas requiring further research, policy incentives, and investment. While substantial overlap existed between climate zones, techniques minimizing soil disturbance (e.g., reduced tillage intensity and frequency) proved more effective in Mediterranean regions with higher erosion risks. The study recommends investment in training and education for future farmers, along with targeted funding to mitigate financial risks associated with adopting soil health practices like reduced tillage and diversified crop rotations. The authors conclude that while promising management strategies have been identified to support soil health business models, further innovation in land management is necessary to achieve sustainable and commercially viable soil management practices.

Graphical summary of practices according to the soil health benefit and economic barrier in cool temperate and Mediterranean climate zones: practices with high benefit but economic barrier are highlighted in green, while high benefit and high economic barrier are highlighted in red.

2. Introduction

There is increasing public and supplier pressure on land managers to manage their soil in a way which is both productive and sustainable. Farm management practices furthermore need to supply nutritious food to a growing global population in the face of an increasingly unstable climate and volatile economic conditions. Management practices which preserve or improve the health of the underlying soils may increase the resilience of land management systems and furthermore provide important ecosystem services, thus there is interest in how best to incentivise soil health-friendly land management practices.

Soil health, or quality, can be broadly defined as ‘the capacity of a living soil to function within natural or managed ecosystems, to sustain plant and animal productivity, maintain or enhance water and air quality, and promote plant and animal health’ (Doran, 2002). Soil health is transient; it can be improved or enhanced by land use and management decisions that consider the multiple functions of soil, but has often been degraded by decisions which focus only on short-term crop productivity (Doran, 2002). Thus, the preservation and improvement of the health of managed soils requires an adjustment in management of soils which are currently in a degraded state. Preserving soil health necessitates maintaining its physical, chemical, and biological attributes, which can be achieved through the implementation of diverse agronomic strategies. This may be through low soil organic matter and/or compaction and erosion, often as a result of long-term arable cropping. Enhancing soil health can be attained through strategies such as diversifying nutrient inputs with a focus on organic sources, adopting conservation agriculture principles, boosting soil microbial diversity, optimizing resource cycling within integrated farming systems, and rectifying soil pH through amendment applications (Shahane & Shivai, 2021).

Reduction of tillage intensity, cultivation of cover crops and incorporating trees and hedgerows into farming systems have been proposed to aid the balance of food production and soil health in agricultural systems. Concurrently, the market for carbon offsetting and credits has led to commercial interest in the theory that management practices which improve soil health could also lead to carbon accumulation. There are currently businesses operating in the carbon credits market based on expected accumulation from implementing these practices, however rates of carbon accumulation are highly variable, and soil health itself should be viewed as a separate entity to soil organic carbon.

Soil carbon itself is a complex constituent part of the soil overall, forming the basis of many important soil processes and interactions from microbial communities to the overall soil structure. The role of carbon within the soil – and of soil management in the accumulation, storage and sequestration of carbon – has come under increasing public scrutiny and commercial interest since the well-publicised “4-per-mille” incentive was launched at COP21 (Minasny et al., 2017). However, there is a key lack of evidence and scientific consensus on the mechanisms that control organic carbon dynamics in soil and thus the ability of soil to store carbon in the long term which can lead to confusion amongst researchers, policymakers, and land managers (Derrien et al., 2023). Furthermore, there is a need for researchers to carefully distinguish between sequestration and storage when discussing soil carbon in the context of management, with research

showing that carbon storage exceeds long-term sequestration despite the terms being frequently used interchangeably (Baveye et al., 2023).

The complexity of interactions between soil variables across a range of scales and lack of a clear set of suitable indicators from which to assess soil health means that assessing soil health is challenging, causing potential confusion to land managers and businesses engaging in soil health improving projects. The assessment of soil health uses a combination of physical, chemical and biological properties (Bünemann et al., 2018; Fahad et al., 2022). These properties serve as indicators of soil function because it is difficult to measure function directly, and observations may be subjective. Soil health properties can be linked to key soil functions and the delivery of public goods and ecosystem services, such as improved water quality, flood alleviation and climate change mitigation (Rinot et al., 2019). There is therefore a clear need for evidence-based approaches to sustainable soil management.

There are many published papers, books and technical documents which provide valuable information for land managers in terms of soil health properties underlying varying land management practices, however used and proposed indicators vary. In research aiming to recommend a minimum dataset of soil indicators, the average number of proposed indicators is 11 (Bünemann et al., 2018). The most frequently used indicators are organic matter (or organic carbon) and pH followed by structural indicators (e.g. water holding capacity, bulk density), soil texture, and available nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium) (Bünemann et al., 2018; Nunes et al., 2021). Furthermore, the heterogeneity of soil systems, climate and topography means that the applicability of findings to European land management systems is not always clear.

This report synthesizes existing literature to assess the potential of new land management practices for improving soil health. Specifically, it examines published evidence on how soil health properties respond to changes in management practices. The report further considers the impact of contextual factors like soil type, sampling depth, and climate on previously published results. This analysis aims to identify existing technologies and practices with the most significant (magnitude) and reliable (certainty) improvements for soil health.

Land use is divided into three categories: agriculture, forestry, and urban environments. The urban category encompasses green spaces, including public parks, gardens, allotments, and road verges, as well as brownfield remediation and development operations that involve soil capping. The report acknowledges the role of agri-environment schemes, established business models that have driven many of the interventions considered. It explores the suitability of management practices for adoption by land managers and proposes strategies to encourage their acceptance for a future of sustainable soil management.

The comparison of quantitative soil data with results from acceptance studies enables the report to consider the social factors behind soil health improving land management practices in a European context, and the current state of acceptance amongst farmers for the practices found to be most suitable for improving soil health.

2.1 Aims and Objectives

The report aims to conduct an in-depth review of management practices to improve soil health across agricultural, forestry and urban land uses. Furthermore, the report aims to examine the acceptance of these practices by land managers and assess any barriers which may be in place. This aim is met through achieving the following objectives:

- Identifying operational soil health indicators from the WPI conceptual framework D1.1.
- Reviewing available land management technologies and practices for soil health management and improvement.
- Evaluating existing technologies and practices with the most significant (in terms of magnitude) and certain (in terms of variability) improvements for soil health.
- Identifying the interactions between climate zones and soil management, thus the most effective strategies soil health improvement in different climate zones.
- Identifying key public and private actors for soil health management support
- Screening relevant farmer and sectoral acceptance studies for soil health improving technologies and practices
- Identifying barriers to acceptance of the most effective practices to target future work

3. Methods

3.1 Literature Search

The report utilized three academic literature databases – Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar – to ensure a comprehensive capture of potential management techniques. The initial search employed the terms "soil (health OR quality)" and "agriculture." Duplicate studies identified across databases were removed, and remaining entries were assessed for suitability based on pre-defined inclusion criteria (detailed in Table 1). To ensure relevance to European farming systems, global studies were limited to those with data obtained from European locations. Finally, studies exclusively presenting model results without quantitative soil data were excluded.

Table 1: the inclusion criteria used for the first search of the academic literature.

Characteristic	Inclusion Criteria
Study Type	Primary research article Review article Conference proceeding Technical document Book chapter
Experimental Design	Control treatments Minimum of duplicated treatments Field scale
Language	English
Location	Europe

The study compiled an extensive database encompassing soil, site, and management variables. Site information included elevation, average annual precipitation, average temperature, study duration, location coordinates, implemented management practices, cropping sequences, control treatment locations, and their management practices. Soil data encompassed characteristics such as soil type, texture, and sampling depth. It further included variables related to soil health and function. These included measurements of pH, bulk density, soil organic matter (SOM), soil organic carbon (SOC), macronutrients, and trace elements. The land use types considered in the study were croplands, forestry, and urban environments.

3.2 Land use type and soil health

The analysis and results were segregated by land use type due to the recognition that soil health has distinct definitions for cropland, forestry, and urban areas. Aligning with the D1.1 Conceptual Framework, the study employed various indicators to assess soil health characteristics specific to each land use type.

For cropland, these indicators included SOC (soil organic carbon), nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), pH, heavy metals, erodibility measured through soil loss, bulk density, and soil biodiversity. The report acknowledges the significance of soil biodiversity in maintaining soil health and the need to develop functional indicators for its monitoring. However, the absence of widely applicable indicator

species across all land-use types presents a challenge, and this area remains under development.

In urban areas, the focus was on trace elements, biodiversity, and compaction. Forestry relied on indicators like N, P, aluminium (Al), trace elements, biodiversity, and compaction (detailed in Table 2).

Table 2: a summary of the soil health indicators included for each land use type (all used in the D1.1 conceptual framework)

Soil Threat	Land Use Type	Proposed Indicator
Soil organic carbon loss	Agriculture	SOC %
		SOC:clay ratio
	Forestry	Soil C:N ratio
		Soil N:P ratio
Soil acidification	Agriculture	pH
Soil pollution	All land uses	Trace elements
		Organic pollutants (e.g. pesticides, biocides, pharmaceuticals)
Soil biodiversity loss	In development	
Soil compaction	All land uses	Bulk density

For each management practice and land use type, results ranges are reported for the available indicators.

3.3 Soil Health Indicators and Climate Zones

The literature review identified that soil health, as measured by selected properties, naturally varies across climate zones, and not all indicators are universally applicable (Zwetsloot et al., 2021). Therefore, the study compared data from two prevalent European climate zones identified in the literature search: cool temperate and Mediterranean. Recognizing the influence of local environmental conditions and potential trade-offs between soil functions, the study acknowledges the unrealistic expectation of achieving optimal performance across all chosen indicators for every soil.

Map of sites included in the review and analysis.

3.4 Literature Search on Soil Health Practices' Acceptance

A separate literature review was conducted on studies examining the acceptance (likelihood of farmer adoption) of soil health practices. For this, Google Scholar was used. The keywords used were “soil health”, “soil practices”, “sustainability”, “adoption”, and “acceptance”. 159 studies were found focussing on the acceptance of soil health practices. Most of those presented research on the African continent. As the agricultural context differs significantly from the European one, we use only the 50 studies carried out on European land management systems. Studies investigated the acceptance of sustainable soil management practices by farmers in general, tillage systems, cover crops and crop rotation, as well as nutrient management and organic farming. Additional studies covered urban farming and agroforestry.

4. Results

The findings are presented in a land-use specific format. For each category (agriculture, forestry, and urban), the report details relevant soil health indicators, followed by soil organic carbon (SOC) results. The concluding section for each land-use type explores the adoption and acceptance of recommended management practices.

4.1. Agricultural Management Practices

The management practices for agricultural land were divided into eight categories and 20 subcategories (Table 3).

Table 3: a summary of management practices for agriculture included in the review.

Updated category	Sub-category	Definition
Agroforestry	Agroforestry	Planting of tree species in arable farmland NOT for biofuel (e.g. in set aside land, field margins, headlands and silvoarable systems)
	Silvopasture	Planting of tree species in pasture
	Hedgerows	Planting of hedgerows
Biofuel Cropping	Woody biomass	Planting of woody biomass for biofuel production (e.g. short rotation coppicing), most commonly willow, poplar
	Arable biofuel	Planting of annual crops for biofuel production (e.g. maize)
Cover Crops	Grass Cover Crop	Planting of grass species/mixtures as a cover crop (e.g. ryegrass)
	Legume Cover Crop	Planting of legume species/mixtures as a cover crop (e.g. white clover)
	Brassica Cover Crop	Planting of brassica species/mixtures as a cover crop (e.g. radish)
	Other Cover Crop	Planting of other species and species mixtures as a cover crop (e.g. vetch)
Grazing	Grazing	Inclusion of grazing animals in arable farmland (e.g. sheep grazing in ley periods, compared with leys which were not grazed)
Leys in Arable Rotations	Leys in arable rotations	Use of temporary ley periods in arable rotations. Ley periods typically range from 1 – 3 years in length
Organic Farming	Organic farming	Adherence to standards of an organic farming certification body: typically mixed farms with no synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides & other agrichemicals utilised. Rock phosphate and inoculant may also be prohibited.
Soil Amendments	Synthetic fertilisers	Use of synthetic fertilisers
	FYM	Use of farmyard manures and slurries, if known the type is listed
	Crop residues	Use of crop residues, typically through chopping and reincorporation
	Biochar	Use of biochar
	Other	Use of amendments not incorporated in previous categories (e.g. digestate, crushed silicate, sludge)
Tillage	Inversion tillage	Tillage in which inversion (typically with moldboard plough) is specified
	Conventional tillage	Annual tillage to a depth >25 cm, typically includes inversion
	Reduced tillage	Either tillage which is not annual or tillage to a depth <25 cm, with no inversion
	Zero tillage	No tillage, typically direct drilling used

The results showed that the body of academic research was not evenly divided between the different management practices, with more studies focussed on tillage than any other management practice and incorporation of grazing animals into arable cropping sequences the least studied in the agricultural management categories (Figure 1).

Figure 1: a summary of datapoints collated according to each agricultural management practice.

A review of acceptance study topics showed that in European land management systems, the most studied areas were conservation/organic agriculture, general land management and training/advice/business models/finance (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Number of topics region examined by studies in Europe that were reviewed (studies that did not investigate specific soil practices are not included).

4.1.3 Agricultural Soil Health

To ensure clarity of results for soil health variables, management sub-categories were arranged into groups based on the underlying management principles of each practice (Table 4).

Table 4: a summary of management themes and their associated sub-categories.

Management Theme	Sub-category
Standard Agricultural Practice	Inversion Tillage
	Conventional Tillage
	Synthetic Fertilizers
Diversify crops	Woody biomass
	Arable Biofuel
	Leys in arable rotations
	Organic farming
Integrate Livestock	Livestock in arable rotations
	FYM
	Silvopasture
Maintain Living Roots	Cereal Cover Crop
	Grass Cover Crop
	Legume Cover Crop
	Brassica Cover Crop
	Other Cover Crop
	Hedgerows
	Agroforestry
Protect Soil Surface	Residues
	Reduced Tillage
	Zero Tillage
Novel Amendments	Biochar
	Other

Management groups were used to compare soil health responses with standard agricultural practice (Figure 3). Groups were based on the principals of regenerative agriculture, a movement of farm management that has been highly successful in encouraging the agricultural land managers, the food industry and policy makers to consider how to best to manage agricultural soils to improve soil health or maximise the delivery of ecosystem services (EASAC, 2022; Khangura et al., 2023). We found that the response of key soil health indicators to different management principles was different between the cool temperate and Mediterranean climate zones (Figure 3).

Figure 3: a summary of soil carbon accumulation rate (annual $t\ ha^{-1}$) soil organic matter (%), bulk density ($g\ cm^{-3}$) and pH for each management principal compared with the standard agricultural practice for cool temperate (red line) and Mediterranean (blue line) climate areas. Note that for carbon accumulation, the median accumulation rate for standard agricultural practice in both climate zones is 0.0 (annual $t\ ha^{-1}$).

The study found that there were higher carbon accumulation rates in cool temperate climates compared to Mediterranean climates for treatments utilizing novel amendments (e.g., biochar) and other miscellaneous amendments (e.g., sewage sludge, anaerobic digestate) (Figure 3). This trend aligns with the generally higher SOM content observed in cool temperate zones (Figure 4b). Notably, novel amendments were the only management practice exhibiting a clear distinction in carbon accumulation rates between the two climate zones (Figure 4a).

Regarding bulk density, the integration of livestock and the year-round presence of living roots in Mediterranean systems resulted in significantly lower values (0.12 and $0.1\ g\ cm^{-3}$ reduction, respectively) compared to control treatments (Figure 4c). In contrast, cool temperate zones displayed the lowest bulk densities in soils

treated with novel amendments and in arable land integrated with livestock. Interestingly, practices aimed at surface protection, such as reduced tillage intensity compared to standard agricultural practices, did not lead to lower bulk densities in either climate zone (Figure 4c).

The study identified higher soil pH levels in Mediterranean climates compared to cool temperate zones, likely due to the acidifying effect of higher rainfall in the latter (Keresztesi et al., 2019) (Figure 4d). Interestingly, Mediterranean plots implementing diversified cropping systems and livestock integration exhibited lower pH compared to standard farming practices in the same region. Conversely, no significant influence of management practices on soil pH was observed in cool temperate zones. This could be attributed to two potential factors. Firstly, soil pH in these zones might already be closer to the optimal range for plant growth. Secondly, factors like parent material, rainfall patterns, fertilizer use, and lime application (Müller et al., 2022) likely exert a stronger influence on soil pH than management activities not directly related to fertilizer or lime amendments.

4.1.2 Agricultural Soil Carbon

The study employed SOC (soil organic carbon) accumulation rates as a key indicator of soil health. In instances where the studies themselves did not report these rates, calculations were made using data on SOC content, bulk density, and sampling depths. Notably, the analysis revealed a trend of higher soil carbon accumulation rates when multiple land management practices were implemented concurrently, as compared to single practices (Table 4). However, the limited number of studies investigating the combined effect of four practices (only two studies within the database) highlights the need for further research in this area. This additional research would be crucial to definitively establish the significance of combining multiple practices for enhanced soil health and SOC accumulation.

Table 5: descriptive statistics of the carbon accumulation rates arranged according to the number of management factors included in the studies analysed.

Number of Management practices adopted	Mean C accumulation (annual t ha ⁻¹)	Median C accumulation (annual t ha ⁻¹)	Min C accumulation (annual t ha ⁻¹)	Max C accumulation (annual t ha ⁻¹)	SE M	SD
1	0.17	0.03	- 8.22	7.65	0.06	0.95
2	0.10	0.11	- 16.00	11.00	0.20	2.54
3	0.12	0.11	- 8.22	4.56	0.20	1.45
4	1.38	1.38	0.07	2.69	1.31	1.85

Studies incorporated a range of sampling depths. The most common soil depth was 30 cm. Results showed that median rates across all depths were less than 0.6 annual t ha⁻¹ (Figure 2). The accumulation rates were highly variable between the sampling depths with the highest average rate of 0.63 annual t ha⁻¹ recorded from a 75 cm depth soil profile and the lowest average rate of - 0.19 annual

t ha⁻¹ from a 30 cm depth soil profile (Figure 2). This finding highlighted the importance of sampling below the topsoil (typically defined as the top 30 cm of the soil) and furthermore the contribution of the subsoil to soil health and carbon storage in agricultural areas. A consideration is that soil depth varies widely across Europe, with some shallow soils of only ~50cm total depth, compared with others which are much deeper.

Figure 4: Agricultural soil carbon accumulation rates according to the sample depth.

Results showed a huge variation in accumulation and loss of SOC in both climate zones across the most sampled depth (30 cm). This variability in rates achieved presents significant challenges to land managers hoping to base income streams on soil carbon accumulation.

The study identified greater variability in carbon accumulation rates for sites with clay content between 0% and 20% (Figure 3). No clear trend emerged from the data to suggest a direct influence of clay content on annual soil carbon accumulation rates. While past research indicates that high-clay soils generally exhibit greater capacity for retaining soil carbon (Matus, 2021), this study suggests that SOC accumulation rates are not inherently higher in clay-rich soils. Furthermore, a growing body of evidence suggests that relying solely on particle size for clay content classification, without considering chemical composition, may lead to inaccuracies. Consequently, soils categorized as having high clay content may not necessarily possess a consistent ability to retain soil carbon (Tan et al., 2017; Mäkipää et al., 2024).

Figure 5: Carbon accumulation rates plotted according to reported soil clay content (%). Note that only studies which reported clay content are included ($n = 1264$).

The analysis revealed variations in the impact of specific practices on carbon accumulation rates between climate zones. In Mediterranean regions, cover crops demonstrated a greater positive influence on carbon accumulation compared to cool temperate zones (Table 5). Similarly, reductions in tillage intensity, transitioning from inversion to zero tillage, yielded larger increases in carbon accumulation rates within the Mediterranean climate (Table 5). Conversely, studies on biochar amendments reported significantly higher carbon accumulation rates in cool temperate zones compared to their Mediterranean counterparts (Table 5). These findings emphasize the critical role of minimizing soil disturbance and maintaining living ground cover (e.g., through cover crops) in preventing soil degradation within Mediterranean climates. This is likely due to the increased vulnerability of Mediterranean soils to erosion.

Table 6: Mean annual soil carbon accumulation rates in agricultural land use according to management type and climate zone.

Cool temperate		Mediterranean	
Sub-category	Mean Annual C accumulation (t ha ⁻¹)	Sub-category	Mean Annual C accumulation (t ha ⁻¹)
Agroforestry	-0.05 [-0.15, 0.14]	Agroforestry	0.32 [0.13, 0.35]
Silvo-pasture	-0.18 [-0.55, 0.39]	Silvo-pasture	-0.29 [-0.49, -0.09]
Hedgerows	0.23 [0.00, 0.27]	Hedgerows	0.21 [-0.29, 0.58]
Woody biomass	0.36 [0.00, 1.40]	Woody biomass	0.43 [0.00, 0.31]
Arable Biofuel	0.00 [-0.44, 0.86]	Arable Biofuel	0.0 [-0.18, 0.36]
Grass Cover Crop	-0.01 [0.00, 0.59]	Grass Cover Crop	0.29 [0.15, 0.43]
Legume Cover Crop	0.01 [-0.12, 0.27]	Legume Cover Crop	0.25 [0.05, 0.30]
Brassica Cover Crop	-0.27 [-0.48, -0.04]	Brassica Cover Crop	1.30 [0.85, 1.73]
Other Cover Crop	0.29 [-0.02, 0.50]	Other Cover Crop	-
Livestock in arable rotations	-0.01 [-0.01, 0.38]	Livestock in arable rotations	0.34 [0.14, 0.49]
Leys in arable rotations	0.21 [0.03, 0.34]	Leys in arable rotations	-0.08 [-0.57, 0.87]
Organic farming	-0.28 [-0.52, 0.03]	Organic farming	-0.72 [-0.89, -0.11]
Synthetic Fertilizers	0.08 [0.00, 0.15]	Synthetic Fertilizers	0.02 [-0.04, 0.09]
FYM	0.46 [0.16, 0.51]	FYM	0.17 [-0.01, 0.29]
Residues	0.74 [0.21, 1.09]	Residues	0.57 [-0.65, 1.36]
Biochar	2.06 [0.99, 3.19]	Biochar	0.13 [0.00, 0.17]
Other	1.80 [0.71, 2.52]	Other	-
Inversion Tillage	-0.78 [-0.45, 0.06]	Inversion Tillage	-0.18 [-0.62, 0.02]
Conventional Tillage	-0.25 [0.00, 0.33]	Conventional Tillage	0.06 [0.00, 0.10]
Reduced Tillage	-0.04 [-0.04, 0.82]	Reduced Tillage	0.10 [-0.64, 0.17]
Zero Tillage	0.03 [-0.12, 0.30]	Zero Tillage	0.24 [0.00, 0.58]

Results showed that the cultivation of woody biomass in farmland (through agroforestry, woody biomass cultivation and hedgerows) was consistently positive in Mediterranean climate areas (Table 5).

4.1.3 Acceptance of Agricultural Soil Management Practices

Barão et al. (2019) studied the adoption rates of sustainable soil management practices in 10 study sites across Europe. They identified crop rotation, manuring

and composting and minimum tillage as the most commonly adopted practices in the selected study sites. These practices are supported through both current and historic implementation of agri-environment incentives across Europe (e.g. the Common Agricultural Policy for 2023 – 27, and summarised by European Commission, 2017).

In a case study in Western Sicily, 14 soil conservation practices were investigated and distinguished according to whether they were promoted under the Rural Development Program. They found that minimum tillage was the most frequently adopted practice of those not included in the Rural Development Program. Organic manuring covered by the Rural Development Program and was the most frequently adopted practice overall, highlighting the key role played by public agri-environment schemes (Fantappiè et al., 2020). In terms of soil carbon, a survey of 435 Dutch arable farmers by Hijbeek et al. (2018) found 90% of the farmers reported a high intention to increase soil organic carbon content in their fields. This suggests that, in principle, many farmers are willing to adopt practices that promote soil health. On the other hand, the responses received by Hijbeek et al. (2018) also indicate that farmers might perceive soil organic carbon content to be largely beyond their control.

Tillage Acceptance

Reduced tillage is one of the most widespread soil sustainability practices among farmers. However, there are differences in adoption across farm-type zones and countries. Bijttebier et al. (2018) found adoption rates to vary from 19% to 80% across four European countries. For arable farms, adoption rates ranged from 68-84% in Germany, 41% in Italy, 54% in the Netherlands, and 23% in Belgium. Differences were due to farm type, geophysical conditions, and cultural, political, and socio-economic conditions. In the Netherlands and Belgium, no-till practices were more commonly implemented by arable farms than dairy farms (54% arable vs. 26% dairy, and 23% vs. 19%, respectively).

The main motives for using reduced tillage are reductions in labour and fuel (Blanco-Canqui & Wortmann, 2020; Bijttebier et al., 2018; Bijttebier et al., 2014; Sattler and Nagel, 2010). Compared to conventional tillage, reduced tillage saves time during work peaks. However, farmers may also adopt reduced tillage for soil health improvement when the benefits are clear: through reduced risk of nitrate leaching (Blanco-Canqui & Wortmann, 2020; Sattler and Nagel, 2010), or erosion reduction in areas which are susceptible (Nandan et al., 2019; Bijttebier et al. 2014). In a study of Spanish olive groves with a high erosion risk, 43% of the farmers surveyed used mulch tillage (a combination reduced tillage and chopped pruning residues as mulch) (Calatrava and Franco, 2011). Relevant adoption factors identified were the farmer's experience and the level of local soil degradation, indicating the relevance of local geophysical conditions to farmer adoption of soil health improving technologies and practices.

Reduced tillage is seen as risk-associated. Non-adopters believe that reducing tillage harms soil health and reduces yields through compaction, resulting poorer growing conditions for cereals (Bijttebier et al., 2014). Farmers fear that reducing tillage will result in more field weeds (Bijttebier et al., 2018; Bijttebier et al., 2014; Sattler and Nagel, 2010). This can reduce yields, especially on poorly draining soils (Bijttebier et al., 2014). In viticulture, farmers using irrigation were found to be less

likely to reduce tillage (Payen et al., 2022). Furthermore, farmers may fear the increased occurrence of fungi, affecting product quality (Bijttebier et al., 2014; Sattler and Nagel, 2010). The limited availability of technology for no-till methods is an adoption barrier (Bijttebier et al., 2014; Mills et al., 2020), thus the costly investments required are another obstacle (Mills et al., 2020).

Prager and Posthumus (2010) and Brown et al., (2020) found a positive association between farm size and likelihood of adopting reduced tillage. A possible explanation is that managers of larger farms are more willing to invest in new technologies such as direct seed drills (Knowler and Bradshaw, 2007). In addition, large farms also have a higher ability to absorb risk (Serebrennikov et al., 2020).

Soil Amendment Acceptance

An exploratory study in several European countries found that some farmers lack necessary knowledge about the benefits of retaining crop residues; in addition, farmers might lose income if the straw can be profitably sold to, e.g., mushroom producers or livestock farmers for bedding (Mills et al., 2020). Organic fertilisers are widely used in mixed systems, where farmers have supply readily available onsite. Still, several potential obstacles exist to using organic fertilisers to improve soil health. Mills et al. (2020) found organic fertilisers had higher costs for arable farms due to logistical challenges and the labour associated with transportation and application. In some European countries (Italy, Hungary), stringent regulations on transport and application are barriers to wider adoption. Spreading of organic fertilisers can ignite conflicts with residents in populated or touristic areas due to odour nuisance (Mills et al., 2020).

Organic Farming Acceptance

Organic systems are perceived as environmentally friendly and are generally preferred by the public (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018; Specht et al., 2016). More than 80% of respondents in Italy would buy products from sustainable farming systems, while there is hardly any support for the use of genetically modified organisms (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). The adoption of organic agriculture was found to be influenced by social norms in a French study of 243 farmers (Mzoughi et al., 2011). Social concerns drove the desire of farmers to demonstrate their environmental commitment to the public, thus adoption of organic farming. Farmers' moral concerns (the individual's ethics) also have been found as a significant driver of organic farming adoption (Mzoughi et al., 2011; Xia et al., 2023). However, these social drivers vary between regions. In Ireland, attitudes of the farmer and farming community towards organic farming were found to constrain its adoption (Läpple and Kelley, 2013).

Other important individual factors for switching to organic farming have been identified with age and education. In a study on olive cultivation in Greece, Chatzimichael et al. (2014) found non-monotonous relationships between the age and the education of the farm manager with the adoption propensity. While farmers above a certain age no longer consider changing their farm management, young farmers might lack sufficient experience to make the switch. Similarly, the level of education was found to decrease adoption probability beyond a certain threshold.

Besides social and farmer-individual factors, economic considerations have a central role in the organic farming (and indeed all soil health improving) adoption decisions. Mzoughi et al., (2011) found that farmers prioritising economic concerns were less willing to implement organic farming, perceiving of organic farming as both more costly and riskier than conventional farming. In Latvia and Estonia, economic factors such as availability of agri-environmental subsidies was more effective in stimulating organic farming uptake than social factors (Kaufmann et al., 2009; Krajewski et al., 2024).

Crop Rotation and Cover Crop Acceptance

A sufficiently diverse crop rotation can support diverse micro and macro faunal communities in the soil, making cultivated plants more resilient (Barão et al., 2019). In a study on viticulture, Payen et al. (2022) identified the size of the farm, available resources, and confidence were key factors for the adoption of cover cropping. While available resources and confidence had a positive influence on adoption, farm size had a negative influence on adoption. Barriers to the uptake of cover crops can be economic aspects, like increased costs due to seeds and extra field operations, although these are lower than those for agroforestry adoption (Mills et al., 2020). Other barriers are a lack of awareness of the benefits of cover crops, or time conflicts, cover cropping leads to additional operations. In drier climate zones and those with climatic restrictions, there are also concerns about water competition between cover crops and spring crops or climatic restrictions (Mills et al., 2020).

Agroforestry Acceptance

Despite their demonstrated environmental benefits, the costliness in implementation of agroforestry paired with poor financial incentives, lack in awareness and education, and insufficient marketing are significant barriers to farmer adoption (Sollen-Norrlin et al., 2020). There are differences in agroforestry system perception between farmers in Mediterranean and cool temperate zones (Graves et al., 2008): while the most relevant factor for Mediterranean farmers was farm profitability, cool temperate farmers were driven to adoption of agroforestry for perceived environmental benefits (Graves et al., 2008). Barriers to adoption were fears of intercrop yield decline and complexity along with necessary mechanization, respectively.

The most popular positive effects of agroforestry cited by stakeholders in Europe were benefits for biodiversity, animal health and welfare, as well as landscape aesthetics (García de Jalón et al., 2018). Most important negative aspects were increased labour and management costs, system complexity, and administrative burden. This result was partly confirmed by Tsonkova et al. (2018) in interviews with German farmers; the administrative and legal burdens were named as the most relevant obstacles. Felton et al. (2023) studied farmer acceptance of agroforestry in England and found that farm ownership was positively associated, while profitability and perception by others was negatively associated with adoption.

Rois-Díaz et al. (2018) found that many farmers used forms of agroforestry without being aware of the concept. Important adoption factors for both adopters and non-adopters were identified to be the desire to stick to traditional farming systems and a lack of awareness. There is evidence to suggest that agroforestry

adoption will increase in the medium to long-run as a response to extreme weather events. The potential of agroforestry to increase farming system resilience to extreme weather events was highlighted as a positive adoption driver in a recent study on Southeast German farmers (Stetter and Sauer, 2022).

4.2. Forestry Results

The key threats facing forest soils were found to be nutrient loss, acidification, pollution, compaction and biodiversity loss (Table 2, D1.1 Conceptual Framework).

4.2.1 Management Practices

The management practices for forest land were divided into four categories and 11 subcategories (Table 7).

Table 7: Summary of categories and definitions in the forest land use type.

Category	Sub-category	Definition
Timber harvesting	Logging and felling	Logging and felling of selected stands
	Reduced impact logging	Use of mapping, planning and technologies to minimize impacts of logging and felling
Stand management	Thinning	Removal of selected trees or parts of trees within woodland to ensure fastest rate of woodland growth
	Herbivore regulation	Control or culling of potentially destructive herbivores
	Species	Selection and management of tree species
	Coppicing	Cutting trees back to the stump to stimulate new growth for timber
	Pollarding	Regular cutting of upper branches to encourage dense foliage at the top of the tree
Reforestation	Artificial regeneration	Introducing new trees through planting of selected seeds or saplings
	Natural regeneration	Introducing new trees through allowing dispersal from existing trees and shrubs
Disturbance	Site operations	Disturbance through use of heavy machinery, creation of tracks and associated forestry operations
	Fire management	Disturbance to stand through prescribed burning or wildfires

The report acknowledges that the term "reduced impact logging" encompasses management practices already considered standard in numerous European forestry operations. These practices include utilizing pre-determined logging paths, relying on topographical maps, and implementing tree selection based on factors like height, slope, and local climatic conditions (Putz et al., 2008).

4.2.2 Forestry Soil Carbon

Almost half of all terrestrial organic carbon is stored in forest biomass and soils (Mayer et al., 2020). In European climate zones, the organic carbon stored in forestry soils far exceeds that which is stored in biomass, particularly in cool temperate and boreal moist zones (Figure 5). This may be attributed in part to far greater biomass

production in tropical climate zones, alongside the necessity of cool conditions to minimize organic carbon losses through decomposition.

Figure 6: Forestry soil carbon content according to biomass (green), subsoil (brown) and topsoil (orange), derived from Scharlemann et al. (2014).

Conversion of arable land to forestry is well known to increase soil carbon content in European climate zones (Mayer et al. 2020). While arable agricultural management has long been established as a threat to soil organic carbon (e.g. Smith et al. 1997; Haddaway et al., 2016), while forestry is largely considered as a carbon sink, there is a large body of evidence to suggest that harvesting operations threaten soil carbon stocks (Achat et al. 2015). We summarise findings from the literature for each sub-category of soil management to outline threats to soil carbon (Table 8).

Table 8: Summary of forest management subcategories and their effect on soil carbon accumulation.

Category	Sub-category	Effect on soil carbon in forestry areas	Source
Timber harvesting	Logging and felling	Negative	Mayer et al., 2020
	Reduced impact logging	Negative	Mayer et al., 2020
	Coppicing	Negative: if residues left, may be mixed	Nave et al., 2010; Camponi et al., 2022
	Pollarding	Mixed: if residues left, positive	Gómez-Muñoz et al., 2016
Stand management	Thinning	No effect	Mayer et al., 2020
	Herbivore regulation	Positive (short term)	Mayer et al., 2020
	Species	No effect	Mayer et al., 2020
Reforestation	Artificial regeneration	Mixed evidence	Jandl et al., 2007; Nave et al., 2024
	Natural regeneration	Mixed evidence	Paul et al., 2002; Nave et al., 2024
Disturbance	Site operations	Negative	Mayer et al., 2020
	Fire management	Mixed evidence	Mayer et al., 2020

Previous reviews and meta-analyses have found that all forms of forestry harvesting have a negative impact on soil organic carbon (Table 8), although thinning activities had no effect on soil carbon. The only forestry management activity which was consistently found to have a positive impact on soil organic carbon was the regulation of herbivorous species in areas of forestry (Table 8, Tanentzap and Coomes, 2012). This work summarised deer exclusion zone studies in Temperate forests across Europe, Asia and North America, and the conclusion of increased carbon stocks was attributed to an $< 1.5 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$ increase in new woody biomass as young trees were protected from browsing by the herbivores. However, authors do note that in other temperate areas (e.g. New Zealand), the long term (decades), evidence is not conclusive for changes in forest carbon stocks with herbivore exclusion (Tanentzap and Coomes, 2012).

4.2.3 Forestry Soil Health

It is well understood that although it enhances workflow efficiency of forestry, mechanized harvesting can cause damage to forest soils. This damage largely through compaction, caused by the size and weight of the machinery involved. Mediterranean soils are the most at risk of compaction in Europe (Ferreira et al., 2022). The degree and durability of damage to forest soils depended on factors including the soil bulk density, site topography and soil texture, moisture and organic matter content (Cambi et al., 2015). The most frequently identified management strategies to limit negative effects of machinery on susceptible soils (referred to in some areas of the literature as “reduced impact logging”) were:

1. Leaving residues on the ground to reinforce the topsoil (e.g. Picchio et al., 2020)
2. Reducing contact pressure between machines and soil through lower tire pressures and larger tires (reviewed by Alakukku et al., 2003)

3. Timing operations in dry conditions to ensure a higher load-bearing capacity in the soil (Picchoi et al., 2020).

As Mediterranean soils are particularly vulnerable to erosion, disturbance through harvesting and cultivation operations leading to soil loss is of particular concern (Ferriera et al., 2022). The minimization of cultivation operations, use of precision equipment for fertilization (such as drones and small aircraft) and application of reduced impact harvesting techniques have all been proposed to minimize the impact of management on soil compaction.

While reforestation is expected to play a key role in climate change mitigation strategies, the impact of forestation management activities on the soil pH is poorly understood. A recent global meta-analysis found that that soil pH declines by 0.23 after forestation activities, regardless of forestation type or any land use changes accounted for due to biologically driven litter decomposition (Huang et al. 2022). Authors found evidence that the decline of pH after forestation was larger in neutral soils than in acidic or alkaline soils. They found that reforestation activities were more likely to contribute to soil acidification in humid boreal and temperate climate regions than arid tropical regions (Huang et al. 2022).

Table 9: Summary of forest management subcategories and their effect on soil acidification.

Category	Sub-category	Effect on soil pH	Source
Timber harvesting	Logging and felling	Acidification	Dahlgren and Driscoll, 1994
	Reduced impact logging	Mixed results: no effect in cool temperate, some evidence for acidification in Mediterranean	Neal et al., 2011 Shah et al., 2022
	Coppicing	Acidification	Lander et al., 2009
	Pollarding	Acidification	Lander et al., 2009
Reforestation	Artificial regeneration	Acidification	Huang et al., 2022
	Natural regeneration	Acidification	Huang et al., 2022

Results from European climate zones showed that reforestation and harvesting led to soil acidification (Table 9), although most studies considered coniferous plantations, which will have a greater acidification effect than deciduous plantations. Furthermore, there was a lack of evidence around stand management and forest disturbance, meaning we were unable to draw conclusions about the impact of these activities on acidification. The impact of reduced impact logging activities was found to be different according to the climate zone, with previous work finding evidence for reduced impact logging having a smaller acidifying effect on forest soils in cool temperate zones than in Mediterranean zones. However, the acidification of soils is highly context specific, with site conditions having a big impact on the outcome of management practices (Figure 6).

Figure 7: Relative importance of moderators for predicting soil pH changes. Moderators include mean annual precipitation (MAP), soil pH before forestation (ipH), years after forestation (Years), site slope (Slope), soil organic C concentration (SOC), forestation type (SOC), soil clay content (Clay) and slope aspect (Aspect).

A recent review found that mean annual precipitation was the most important factor in predicting soil pH changes under forestry management, followed by the starting soil pH before forestation due to a higher acidification effect in soils with a neutral starting pH than those with acidic or alkaline pH (Figure 6).

The risk of management activities exacerbating soil and water pollution is a key threat to forestry soil health. In cool temperate climates, main concerns are associated with soil disturbance and loss from forest cultivation, drainage, road construction and harvesting operations. Furthermore, there are concerns that the aerial fertilizer applications can increase soil phosphate concentrations, thus potentially leading to eutrophication (Nisbet, 2001). Forestry management systems which minimize site disturbance are recognised to be of key importance to this: through minimal cultivation, by ensuring that drainage systems minimize surface runoff, and by restricting furrow lengths and depths to reduce the impact of unavoidable ploughing.

The consensus in the literature is that buffer strips are instrumental in retaining any mobilised sediment on site. It has been well established in the literature for decades that buffer strips play a vital role in reducing sediment losses from upland forestry (Swift and Norton, 1993). However, the effectiveness of buffer strips is dictated by the catchment area of a given drain and the width of strip. For new planting, buffer strips from 5-40 m width are recommended by UK forestry guidelines.

In Mediterranean areas, the impact of forestry management activities on soil health and pollution are impacted by generally lower SOC levels due to climate conditions and long-term anthropogenic activities in this zone (Delcourt et al., 2023). Applications or fertilizers leading to build-up of unwanted nutrients and contaminants are also of concern in Mediterranean zones (Fuentez et al., 2007). There is a lack of consensus on specific technologies and practices to improve the state of soil pollution in forested Mediterranean systems. This is largely because the issues of soil loss and compaction are of a higher concern to researchers, policymakers and the general public in Mediterranean zones (Cutini et al., 2021, Alvarez et al., 2013).

Research in Mediterranean zones has shown that applications of sewage sludges to forestry zones can significantly increase potentially toxic metal concentrations in soils and metal transfer to freshwater and plants (Toribio and Romanya, 2006). Furthermore, the extensive land use history of Mediterranean regions means there are extensive areas of potential contamination with heavy metals, thus a need for forest management to be resilient to soil pollution. Research shows that incorporating a mixture of tree species enhances system resilience at heavy metal polluted sites (Samara et al., 2020). In Mediterranean zones, black pine was found to absorb the highest concentration of iron (Fe), while black poplar had the highest concentrations of zinc (Zn). In general, while both coniferous and broadleaved species had highest concentrations for iron, they differed in terms of their uptake of other trace elements from the soil. For coniferous species the order of concentration was Fe, Zn, manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), chromium (Cr), nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co). In broadleaved species, the order was Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu, Ni, Cr (Samara et al., 2020). Cadmium was detected only in black poplar at both sites, indicating its potential suitability for inclusion in forestry stands where soil cadmium contamination was a concern.

4.2.4 Afforestation Acceptance

Land manager willingness to participate in afforestation measures is largely guided by economic considerations as opposed to soil health considerations. Converting farmland to forest elicits opportunity costs, and even though income after afforestation may be greater than the income achieved through farmland management, the long-term nature of economic return from tree planting is a barrier preventing afforestation from being an economically attractive option (Brouwer et al., 2015; Ryan and O'Donoghue, 2016). Farmers might refrain from afforestation simply because of the desire to cultivate their farmland (Ryan and O'Donoghue, 2016). The suitability of the underlying soil characteristics for tree planting and the economic subsidies received are important factors influencing economic appeal of afforestation to land managers (Ryan and O'Donoghue, 2016). The conversion of agricultural land with the lowest productivity for afforestation may help farmers increase income of the land (Vidyaratne et al., 2020), however as stated, economic benefits are only achievable in the long term unless supported by agri-environmental schemes.

A special characteristic associated with afforestation compared to other soil management practices is the long-term nature of any decision to convert agricultural land to forest (Ryan and O'Donoghue, 2016). In farmland afforestation schemes, the duration the scheme is a decisive factor. Farmers have shown to prefer shorter contracts and highly value the option of converting the land back

into agricultural land after the contract ends, however planting and harvesting of trees takes place over decades (Brouwer et al., 2015; Lienhoop and Brouwer, 2015; Ryan and O'Donoghue, 2016; Vidyaratne et al., 2020). Also, farmers prefer to convert only small areas (Lienhoop and Brouwer, 2015). Providing accurate economic advice has been found to increase farmers' willingness to participate in afforestation schemes (Brouwer et al., 2015; Lienhoop and Brouwer, 2015).

While farm type does not predict participation in afforestation schemes (Brouwer et al. 2015), farm size is a predictor (Ryan and O'Donoghue 2016). This is because farmers with limited land must farm all of it to ensure economic viability, making them reluctant to afforest (Frawley and Leavy, 2001). Larger farms are more likely have a larger revenue base and greater capacity to absorb short-term opportunity costs in favour of long-term benefits. High off-farm income is positively associated with the willingness to participate in afforestation measures (Ryan and O'Donoghue, 2016; Vidyaratne et al., 2020).

Landowners were aware of positive environmental effects of afforestation. German farmers rated forests as important for carbon storage, erosion reduction and clean air/water, all of which have strong links to soil health (Brouwer et al., 2015). However, research conducted in the Netherlands found that farmers placed value only on clean air, and that soil-related ecosystem services do not influence the willingness to participate in an afforestation scheme (Lienhoop and Brouwer, 2015). Besides economic and environmental factors, social norms can determine decision-making (Deuffic et al., 2018).

4.3. Urban Results

The key threats facing urban soils were found to be pollution, compaction and biodiversity loss (Table 2, D1.1 Conceptual Framework).

4.3.1 Management Practices

The management practices for urban land were divided into four categories and 11 subcategories (Table 10).

Table 10: Summary of categories and definitions in the urban land use type.

Category	Sub-category	Definition
Urban forestry	Urban forestry	Cultivation of trees in an urban environment
Green spaces	Parkland	An area of managed parkland, predominantly mown grass
	Improved parkland	Parkland with multi-species swards, trees, wetland areas etc
	Road verges	Grasses and shrubs along roads
	Gardens	Private gardens with lawns, trees etc
	Community gardens	Public gardens with lawns, trees etc
Urban farming	Market gardens	Small scale, typically high intensity horticultural production for commercial use
	Allotments	Small scale horticultural production for largely personal use
Brownfield management	Revegetation	Cultivation of trees, shrubbery or grass in brownfield site
	Remediation	Practices to either prevent the transportation of pollutants or remove pollutants from the brownfield site (e.g. phytoremediation)
	Capping	Constructing impermeable barrier over the soil surface (e.g. a car park)

As with agriculture, research paper numbers were not evenly divided between the different management practices. A recent review found that research into ecosystem services provided by urban soils is a small but growing area, with ~75 papers published from European systems up until 2019 (O’Riordan *et al.*, 2021). It was found that the majority of papers investigating ecosystem services in urban soils focussed on the top 0 – 40 cm (Figure 7).

Figure 8: Summary of sampling depths from papers investigating ecosystem services in urban soils (from O’Riordan et al., 2021).

Review articles and meta-analyses were used to identify common themes.

4.3.2 Urban Soil Health

Cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni) and zinc (Zn) become toxic at large concentrations and are predominant trace element pollutants of urban soil. Pollutants also include arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), lead (Pb) and mercury (Hg). Urban pollutants are largely released as a result of anthropogenic activities including industry, transport, waste, energy and construction (Li et al., 2018). Brownfield management techniques including revegetation, remediation (through organic amendments, phytoremediation or biochar) and surface capping have all been found to reduce concentrations of heavy metals in urban land use areas (Table 11).

Table 11: Summary of management subcategories and their effect on heavy metals in the urban land use type.

Category	Sub-category	Effect on heavy metals in urban areas	Reference
Urban forestry	Urban forestry	Reduction	Irga et al., 2015
Green spaces	Parkland	No effect	Madrid et al., 2002; Beesley et al., 2020
	Improved parkland	-	-
	Road verges	No effect	Piepenschnieder et al., 2015
	Gardens	No effect	Bretzel et al., 2018
	Community gardens	No effect	Hiller et al., 2022
Urban farming	Market gardens	No effect	Mok et al., 2014
	Allotments	No effect	Bretzel et al., 2018; Mok et al., 2014
Brownfield management	Revegetation	Reduction	Cundy et al., 2016
	Remediation	Reduction	Obrycki et al., 2017; Cundy et al., 2016
	Capping	Reduction	Obrycki et al., 2017

The study revealed minimal influence from urban green spaces and farming practices on soil heavy metal concentrations compared to the initial soil properties (Table 11). This aligns with the focus of much existing research on urban food production, which primarily investigates the potential for human activities to contaminate edible crops (e.g., Bretzel et al., 2018).

The most prominent threat to urban soil health is the sealing of the surface, enacted through construction of roads, buildings and other urban developments. This issue is widespread across Europe, with north-western cool temperate regions of particular concern (Figure 8). In 2012, the European Commission published guidelines to promote the limitation, mitigation and compensation of urban soil sealing, acknowledging the damage such management can cause on the function and ecosystem services provided by soils (European Commission 2012). Management practices proposed included simple limitations on land take and planning permission for urban use at a national level, but without legally binding measures, initiatives are not sufficient (European Commission 2012).

Figure 9: Map of soil sealing prevalence in European countries, derived from Stankovics et al., 2020.

The preservation of urban green spaces and planting of diverse species mixtures to include deep rooting structures in parkland and road verges has been suggested to maintain or improve urban soil structure where possible (Segar et al., 2022). Furthermore, the use of organic amendments such as composts or biosolids has been proposed to both remediate anthropogenic contamination and soil compaction (Kumar et al., 2016).

Evidence from the literature showed that implementation of green spaces in urban areas (including parkland, improved parkland, road verges and community gardens) provide mediation from urban heat islands (Kirschner et al., 2023) with positive implications for local biodiversity. A global synthesis of research on urban soil biodiversity found that a combination of disturbances and homogenization of urban ecosystems is leading to homogenization of urban microbial biodiversity: thus while diversity of soil microbiota may be high at a given site, differences in community composition between sites may nonetheless be small (Sun et al., 2023). The analysis summarizes specific management practices which can improve urban soil biodiversity (Figure 9).

Figure 10: Summary of biodiversity-improving urban management practices, derived from Sun *et al.*, 2023.

Nematodes equally abundant in urban than in non-urban systems, however urban nematode species composition shows dominance of fast-growing bacterivores and herbivorous nematodes, at the expense of larger omnivores (Li *et al.*, 2022). There is a general trend in urban systems of more negative effects on larger organisms also applies to larger-sized soil invertebrate groups (Sun *et al.*, 2023).

4.3.3 Urban Soil Carbon

Urban soils are a large terrestrial store of carbon, with a mean SOC stock of 73 t ha⁻¹ and content of 4.3% to a depth of 50 cm (Allroy *et al.*, 2021). This is variable depending on physical factors including climate and topography, but previous analyses have found limited evidence that stocks in urban land cover vary through the soil profile or with vegetation cover (Allroy *et al.*, 2021).

4.3.4 Acceptance Studies in Urban Contexts

In the European urban context, there is a need for further research into acceptance of management practices other than agriculture; as we have not found evidence for urban agriculture improving the health of urban soils. Future work should consider investigating the social and economic acceptability of the other practices explored, like measures for biodiversity improvement (Figure 10) or to prevent soil sealing. There are studies on urban agriculture from Italy, Spain, Germany, and

Poland (Camps-Calvet et al., 2016; Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018; Specht et al., 2016; Sroka et al., 2021). In a study on citizens of Berlin done by Specht et al. (2016), 60% of the respondents indicated previous knowledge of urban agriculture. However, a survey of 380 residents of Bologna by Sanyé-Mengual et al., (2018) showed that urban agriculture was relatively unknown. Over half of those surveyed were unfamiliar with the concept and no socio-demographic variables were found to explain prior knowledge of the concept.

Urban agriculture is supported in theory by most respondents studied. Over 50% of respondents in Bologna favoured all types of urban agriculture with gardens and peri-urban agriculture even showing approval rates of around 90% (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). A lower level of acceptance was observed in a Polish survey of six cities (Sroka et al., 2021), with more than 70% of the 577 participants accepting urban farming. No socio-demographic characteristics could explain the variation in urban farming acceptance in this case. Only the perceived risk and the social distance from agriculture were decisive to some degree (Sroka et al., 2021). More specifically, factors that reduce the acceptance of urban agriculture were found to be risks regarding health and soil-less cultivation methods and clashes with traditional agricultural management (Specht et al., 2016; Sroka et al., 2021).

Among urban green space options, public parks and urban gardens were the most popular in Italy and Germany (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018; Specht et al., 2016). In comparison, meadows were the least popular (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). Residential gardens had a higher acceptance among the population than community or educational gardens (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). In Bologna, aquaponics and vertical farming were more accepted than rooftop gardens (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). In Germany, these high-tech initiatives were the least popular (Specht et al., 2016). While more than 70% of the respondent favoured urban farming, only 52% approved of public support.

Citizens acknowledge ecosystem services generated by urban green spaces and agriculture. Recreation and entertainment, education and training, and "contact with nature and artistic expression were the most valued services in Bologna (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). In several cities, biodiversity and pollination were among the most important services (Camps-Calvet et al., 2016; Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018; Sroka et al., 2021). Emission reduction, increased water efficiency, and improved organic waste recycling were benefits expected by the German and, partly, the Polish respondents (Specht et al., 2016; Sroka et al., 2021). Recognized economic benefits included food security and local production. Important social benefits were education, contact with nature, and visual aspects (Camps-Calvet et al., 2016; Sroka et al., 2021). Ecosystem services with the lowest valuations were the reduction of effects of extreme events, contributions to political realisation and prevention of soil erosion and maintenance of soil fertility (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). This differs, for example, from the study done by Camps-Calvet et al. (2016) in Barcelona, where soil erosion was one of the most important ecosystem services.

5. Integrating Soil Health Findings and Acceptance of Soil Health Improving Practices in Europe

Identifying any gaps between the best strategies identified to improve soil health and their acceptance amongst land managers is key to ensuring the future sustainability of land management strategies in Europe. This section of the report highlights a few general adoption factors for sustainability factors. We bring together both strands of the work conducted: the evidence base for soil health improvements of each management practice, and the corresponding acceptance rate.

Table 12: Summary of the evidence for soil health benefits, likelihood of adoption and economic barriers for selected management practices

Cool temperate climate zones			
Management	Soil health benefit	Likelihood of adoption	Economic barrier
Agroforestry	High	Low	High
Cover Crops	Medium	High	Medium
Crop Rotations	High	High	Medium
Organic Farming	Low	Low	Medium
Organic Amendments livestock/mixed farms	High	High	Low
Organic Amendments arable farms	High	Medium	High
Reduced Tillage	Medium	High	Medium
Afforestation	Medium	Medium	High
Urban forestry	High	Medium	Low
Green spaces	High	High	Medium
Urban farming	Low	Medium	High
Mediterranean climate zones			
Agroforestry	High	Medium	High
Cover Crops	Medium	High	Medium
Crop Rotations	Medium	High	Medium
Organic Farming	Low	Low	Medium
Organic Amendments livestock/mixed farms	Medium	High	Medium
Organic Amendments arable farms	Medium	Medium	High
Reduced Tillage	High	High	Medium
Afforestation	Medium	Medium	High
Urban forestry	Medium	Medium	Low
Green spaces	Medium	High	Medium
Urban farming	Low	Medium	High

A core aspect for acceptance of sustainable practices, like erosion control measures, is the knowledge of potential threats (Biielders et al., 2003; Knowler and Bradshaw, 2007). Knowledge can be generated through agricultural training and advice (Schaub et al., 2023) or experience with practices (Bartkowski and Bartke, 2018). Higher levels of education have been found to increase the number of sustainable

practices implemented on farm (Fantappiè et al., 2020; Erwin Wauters et al., 2010) as well as the acceptance rate of agri-environmental policies (Vanslembrouck et al., 2002).

Based on the summary of soil health, acceptance rates and barriers (Table 12), results allow us to make recommendations for how best to improve uptake of the most promising management practices. For agroforestry, both financial incentives and improved education for farmers about the environmental improvements from adopting the practice are necessary to improve awareness and uptake. At present, converting to agroforestry is very time-consuming, thus there is a need for innovation in the field. Diversifying crop rotation may cause high opportunity costs (e.g. crops with high contribution margins such as root crops are no longer available). In Germany, there are already agri-environmental measures that make compensation payments for more diverse crop rotations. This could be one way of strengthening crop rotation diversification acceptance. However, it is possible that climate change and growing ecosystem instability will lead to a shift towards a more diverse crop rotation anyway.

Organic amendment uptake findings are split between mixed/livestock farms and arable crop farms. Since livestock farms produce liquid manure anyway, they also want to spread it. Economic barriers arise here primarily due to political restrictions. For example, when spreading close to the ground is introduced and farmers need new technology for this. The economic barrier is significantly greater for cash crop farms. Products must be transported there from other farms. Transportation is very expensive, especially over long distances. The problem of low-emission application must also be considered here. In the long term, area-based animal husbandry is a way of ensuring the application of organic nutrients in an optimum quantity ratio. When it comes to the technology required for low-emission spreading, practicable solutions must be found for existing farms. This includes long-term planning security, support for the purchase of new technology or for joining together to form application communities.

Reducing tillage was found to effectively improve soil health in Mediterranean zones, and the review of farmer adoption found that the practice is already widespread. On farms that still work with ploughs, it can be assumed the high level of acceptance and new machines will lead to a switch to conservation seeding methods. The biggest barrier to reduced tillage adoption are not economic, but rather the fear of being confronted with weeds without a plough. Solutions here therefore centre around ensuring that farmers receive adequate training and evidence of success from research stations and living labs to ensure confidence and availability of information and experience.

5.1. Behavioural Factors affecting Likelihood of Adoption

Our recommendations draw from the finding that European farmers are more willing to adopt soil conservation practices if they see other farmers doing it (Prager and Posthumus, 2010). Appreciation by society is an additional factor influencing adoption (Hannus and Sauer, 2021). Regarding the farmer's personal opinions, a pro-environmental attitude increases their willingness to implement soil conservation practices (Bartkowski and Bartke, 2018; Sattler and Nagel, 2010; Schaub et al., 2023). Farmers with a higher lifestyle and social motivation rate opportunity costs for conservation practices lower than farmers with higher

financial and economic motivation (Greiner and Gregg, 2011). On the other hand, farmers can be hesitant to change their behaviour, meaning they want to maintain the existing farm management, as initially learned (Gomes and Reidsma, 2021).

Another frequently discussed factor affecting adoption is risk. Following Dessart et al. (2019), risk can be divided into general personal risk tolerance, a more distal behavioural factor, and the perceived risk of a conservation practice. Most farmers can be expected to be risk-averse, which has been found not just for crop and dairy farms but also permanent crop farms such as olive farms (Hannus and Sauer, 2021; Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2020). Therefore, farmers in general prefer practices that reduce production risk (Bartkowski and Bartke, 2018; Sattler and Nagel, 2010). Risk-taking farmers implement more conservation practices than risk-averse farmers (Greiner and Gregg, 2011). Because training and advice can reduce the perceived risk of a new management practice (Hannus et al., 2020), they can be effective levers to increase uptake of conservation agriculture (Cárceles-Rodríguez et al., 2022).

5.1.3. Farm Characteristics

Besides farm size, other farm characteristics such as the share of non-family employees, the share of rented land, or farm type have been found to be significantly associated with the adoption of soil health improving practices (Fantappiè et al., 2020; Sattler and Nagel, 2010). Bartkowski and Bartke (2018) as well as Sklenicka et al. (2015) observed land tenure to be negatively related to adoption propensity. A reason could be that farmers focus more on productivity than on the soil's long-term health because more cash flow must be generated to pay for land rents. Farmers also consider resource constraints and the compatibility of a practice with existing farm management when deciding whether to adopt conservation practices (Greiner and Gregg, 2011). Advantages in production and management as well as the availability of necessary machinery are strong motives (Bartkowski and Bartke, 2018; Bijttebier et al., 2018).

Of importance are also ecological constraints. Biophysical conditions like soil texture and regional climatic conditions affect adoption (Bijttebier et al., 2018; Sattler and Nagel, 2010). For example, farmers facing higher threats of soil erosion are more likely to implement measures to control soil erosion (Biielders et al., 2003). Farmers cultivating soil in good condition participate with a lower probability in ecosystem schemes with fixed payments, which can be explained by higher opportunity costs compared to land with less favourable soil conditions and lower yield potential (Schaub et al., 2023). Boardman et al. (2003) and Karali et al. (2014) note that, in general, farmers in developed countries are highly influenced by economic incentives. Bureaucratic load, profitability, and opportunity costs are significant factors in decision-making (Bartkowski and Bartke, 2018; Greiner and Gregg, 2011; Hannus and Sauer, 2021; Jaworski et al., 2023).

6. Discussion and Future Considerations

The review has highlighted key management practices which are implemented to improve soil health, as well as the underlying principals which are best suited to facilitating soil health improvements across selected European climate zones. In cropland, results showed that soil health related variables responded differently to interventions: in Mediterranean zones, management activities which maintained

living roots such as cover cropping resulted in lower bulk densities and had higher soil carbon accumulation rates than conventionally managed sites (Breil et al., 2023; Lopez-Vicente et al., 2021), but soil pH was higher than conventional sites (Sanz-Cobena et al., 2006). This example shows the need for site-specific, tailored soil management advice to ensure that the correct soil variables are targeted in each instance.

As is well established in academic literature, the context-specificity of soil health relates to both the physical location and the intended and historic land use of the site (Bünemann et al., 2018). We assessed the soil health underlying contrasting land uses (agriculture, forestry and urban) according to a separate set of variables, established by the D1.2 Conceptual Framework. This was largely based on the differing requirements for plant productivity in forestry and agricultural sites: commonly cultivated coniferous species in cool temperate climates are tolerant to soil acidity but also acidify the soil (Augusto et al., 1998), while shallow rooting cereal crops may be less immediately impacted by deeper structural issues such as subsoil compaction (Nyeki et al., 2016). As outlined in the conceptual framework, the need to monitor and manage soil pollutants and biodiversity are universal irrespective of land use type.

There is a clear need to develop a framework of suitable soil biological indicators for application to biodiversity assessments in a variety of land use types in a European context. Defined by the European Soil Data Centre (Panagos et al., 2022) as “the variation in soil life, from genes to communities, and the ecological complexes of which they are part, that is from soil micro-habitats to landscapes”, and biodiversity is included in the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 definition of soil health, which states that “Soils are healthy when they are in good chemical, biological and physical condition, and thus able to continuously provide as many of the following ecosystem services as possible”, which includes providing the basis for life and biodiversity, including habitats, species, and genes. The Soil Strategy notes that at present soil carbon is widely used and interpreted as a soil biological indicator, but that it does not assess biodiversity directly. The Strategy proposes the development of a European database of soil biota to enable future assessment and monitoring of European sites.

Quite apart from biodiversity, there is a need to acknowledge that although soil carbon is a useful and widely applicable soil health indicator, assessing soil health relies upon a whole range of indicators considering chemical, biological and physical indicators (Bünemann et al., 2018; Rabot et al., 2018). Species of soil macrofauna and mesofauna such as earthworms, beetles or nematodes have been proposed as indicators of soil biological health and diversity for agricultural land in cool temperate climates (Faber et al., 2013). This is due to the ease of sampling when compared to more analytical soil biological indicators, such as DNA analysis, bacterial/fungal colony counts, substrate-induced respiration or microbial community biomass. Furthermore, surveys of macro and mesofauna provide robust, easily-interpretable data which is easily understood by the general public in comparison to analytical counterparts (Stroud, 2019).

We summarised evidence which showed that establishing hedgerows, growing new woody biomass, incorporating biofuel crops into rotations, growing legume cover crops, application of fertilizers, FYM and biochar and reincorporation of crop residues, along with switching to zero tillage, led to positive soil carbon

accumulation rates in both cool temperate and Mediterranean climate zones. This indicates the consistency of soil carbon improvements should such management practices be actioned across wide differences in local climate zones, compared with the other management practices considered.

Variance in soil characteristics across our study zone regardless of management practice similarities shows the importance of context specificity – while the vast majority of studies included within this report did include information relating to the soil type, soil texture, clay content (if texture not given) and sample depth, there were sites which did not report this important information. The prevalence of studies considering only the top 30 cm of the soil (Figure 2) has undoubtedly influenced the results presented in this report. While the topsoil is more likely to be influenced by land management practices in the short term (Gregory et al., 2016), there is a real and pressing need for soil health assessments to consider the impact of management on the subsoil too: there are a growing number of research articles exploring the structural implications of compaction in the subsoil. An important facet of subsoil compaction across all land uses considered is that it is very difficult to remediate once it has occurred (Keller and Or, 2022).

A further consideration is the legacy effects of previous management activities. The studies included in this report reported previous activities in general terms, but a recurring issue was the lack of soil data reported prior to commencement of management activities, meaning that it was difficult to compare contrasting management strategies. This issue is particularly relevant to compaction and contamination by heavy metals and other pollutants, for which previous disturbances or contamination events may have long lasting implications for sustainable soil management (e.g. Nunes et al., 2016).

Studies that identify relationships between land management practices and soil frequently lack consideration of the impacts of technical interventions on soil health. For example, in our analysis we consider the use of cover crops and residues, however the impact of cover crop cultivation on soil health varies depending on how cover crops are terminated: either chemically or through physical destruction. While our analysis seeks to provide clarity on the impact of technological interventions, this is as of yet poorly explored in academic literature (Stokes et al., 2023).

An important consideration of any soil health management guidance is the applicability and utility of advice given to those actively involved in making and actioning land management decisions. There is a clear case for the active participation of land managers in co-designing soil health improving management practices and business models.

6.1 Acceptance of Soil Health Improving Practices

A key issue is how best to increase acceptance rates of soil health improving practices. In addition to legal regulations that restrict land management decisions (such as rules for the application of organic fertilisers), and agri-environment schemes which subsidize implementation of desired farm management practices, there are many voluntary options for farmers that can be used to improve soil health. Because of their voluntary character, the willingness to participate in such measures is an essential factor for the success of the measures. While the

willingness of farmers to participate in voluntary schemes cannot always be directly influenced by policies, two main factors which can be addressed are awareness and economic conditions.

Awareness is a key driver of willingness to participate in soil health improving practices, irrespective of the specific practice. Firstly, farmers must be sufficiently informed about the threats to their soils. This can be, for example, erosion by water and wind or more frequent droughts. Farmers who are aware of the dangers have an incentive to improve resilience of their soils. To apply effective soil practices, it is then essential to have sufficient knowledge about the different practices. Negative preconceptions are often an obstacle, while positive effects are not well known. Greater know-how improves the use of soil health-promoting practices and thus also the effect of the measures.

Increasing awareness positively influences social issues for adoption. A positive image of the practices in society and among farmers increases the willingness of farmers to implement them. Young farmers still in training are an essential target group. It is important to train their successors correctly from the outset. During training, the focus should not only be on production and efficiency. An important goal should also be to create resilient soils. At the same time, consultation programmes should be provided for established farmers. In general, farmers prefer training courses that are adapted to regional conditions and are practice oriented. These could be field days within municipalities but also individual, farm-specific advice. As this is time-consuming and cost-intensive, weighing the costs and benefits of individual counselling is important.

The second decisive factor for accepting conservation practices is the economic aspect. Farmers generally prefer practices that have higher benefits than costs. Benefits can be savings in working time or other resources. Positive effects on soil conditions, yields and product quality are also relevant. Costs for the farmer arise from opportunity costs, such as loss of income because straw is not sold, as found in one study. Additional costs due to investments in new technology are also decisive. The tricky economic characteristic of many soil health practices is that costs are oftentimes more visible than benefits that might only occur in the medium to long-run. For example, the (private) costs of agroforestry systems are relatively large to their (social) benefits (Table 12) . For practices that generate immediate positive benefits for farmers (for example, only little investment required and positive effects on yields), it is essential to communicate and raise awareness of these positive effects. For practices that are more costly for the farmer, for example, due to the need to invest in new technology, incentives must be created to make these practices attractive and to internalise positive ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration. Various business models would be conceivable to achieve this, such as payments for ecosystem services, one-off payments for investments, or the inclusion of value chain actors. It will be important to identify viable business models and their potential in the future.

A unique feature associated with agroforestry measures is the option for farmers to return land to agricultural production. Permanent conversion causes high opportunity costs and is associated with a high personal inhibition threshold. Hereby, the individual nature of the farm determines the opportunity costs. They are influenced by the farm's mechanical equipment, farm orientation (determining, e.g., feed requirements), biophysical conditions, and the farmer's personal attitudes.

Awareness is a crucial aspect of urban soil systems. A key finding from our analysis is the need for further research into soil health underlying urban areas, technologies and practices results, to improve the implementation of soil health business models. Many citizens have yet to become familiar with the practices. However, residents tend to perceive the practices as positive. While some studies have already looked at the acceptance of practices by residents, the question should also be asked in future, as to which other stakeholders are decisive for a high level of implementation of urban systems. Important stakeholders could be the owners of land and buildings and the city administration. To what extent other stakeholders are involved should also be clarified. While citizens are willing to buy products from urban cultivation, they do not generally support public payments for such concepts. Here, too, it is necessary to identify business models that consider all stakeholders' interests to achieve a high acceptance of such models.

7 Conclusions

The report had identified key practices which improve soil health across European climate zones in agricultural, forestry and urban land uses. While accounting for the context specificity of soil properties, we categorised the diversification of crop rotations, use of soil amendments, and growing of new trees in farming and urban contexts as highly beneficial to soil health. A reduction in tillage intensities where possible in Mediterranean soils was also found to have a high soil health benefit. However, of these promising practices, there will be a key role for future research and technological advances to help break down economic and social barriers to adoption, in order to best equip land managers to create sustainable soil health business models. We present evidence that key practices in need of future innovative solutions are agroforestry and novel soil amendments, as these have both a high soil health benefit but high economic barrier for adoption across Europe.

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